

USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR DIGITAL FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

Although numerous studies have addressed fraud detection in financial systems, there remains a significant gap in the literature regarding validated, scalable AI-based models and hybrid automation schemes for financial transaction monitoring. Existing research lacks comprehensive simulation-based evaluations of transition strategies from human-centric oversight to AI-enhanced processes. This study addresses this gap by identifying optimal AI models and simulating hybrid deployment schemes, thereby generating new knowledge for automated fintech oversight. The following methods were used: focus on the subject of the study; normalization of an unbalanced empirical dataset using Z-score; preparation of a training and validation dataset; comparative analysis of models for detecting anomalies in financial transactions; modelling the risk of committing fraud during the monitoring of financial transactions. It was found that AI models, in particular Random Forest (80% Recall, 99.98% Specificity, 99.95% Accuracy, 0.05% Error, $\kappa = 0.842$, Time Cost = 26 s), have significant potential in fintech for detecting fraudulent transactions, and the most effective approach is a hybrid interaction of AI and specialists. The academic novelty of the study is the modelled transition from human monitoring of financial transactions to automation through hybrid schemes, which allows AI to integrate the best practices of specialists. Further research should focus on expanding the range of AI models, using raw datasets without PCA, and improving hybrid interaction schemes in fintech.

Keywords: *Fintech, Fraudulent Transactions, Fraud Detection, Machine Learning, Classification, Empirical Dataset, AI Models.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of this study follows from industry statistics: in 2022, the volume of fraudulent payments in the European Economic Area (EEA) amounted to €4.3 milliard. In the first half of 2023, it reached €2.0 milliard, with the largest fraud being related to credit transfers (€1.131 milliard) and card transactions (€633 million) [1]. In 2024, 269 million bank card records and 1.9 million stolen bank checks were published [2]. In the first half of 2024, fraud worth over £710 million was prevented thanks to

preventive measures, although losses caused by fraud amounted to over £570 million [3]. Finally, global losses from bank card fraud in 2024 will reach about \$35.8 milliard [4]. These data confirm the need for further research in the field of financial transaction monitoring.

Currently, the financial sphere is undergoing a complete digitalization and the formation of a paradigm of the digital financial space [5], [6]. The increasing volume of financial and currency transactions, their complex interrelationships and comprehensive digital

transformation create the problem of controlling the transactions under study, thereby creating a challenge for the entire fintech sphere [7]. The problem of monitoring financial transactions is complicated by the shortage of specialists in the field, which is associated with global challenges and the crisis in the labour market [8], [9].

This study is delimited to the task of optimizing AI-driven approaches for digital financial transaction monitoring, with a particular focus on the classification of fraudulent activities, simulation of detection effectiveness, and validation of AI-based models within the constraints of explainability, accuracy, and risk prediction. The research does not encompass the full regulatory implementation cycle or cover traditional anti-fraud systems outside the AI domain.

The aim of this study is to determine the optimal AI models and schemes for using AI tools for monitoring financial transactions.

To achieve the established goal, it is necessary to perform the following tasks:

- determine the range of AI-based models that can classify financial transactions;
- simulate the functioning of AI algorithms for the effectiveness of detecting fraudulent transactions during the monitoring of financial transactions and determine the most effective AI-based model;
- simulate the risk of fraud during the monitoring of financial transactions and establish the optimal scheme for using AI fintech.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The search for relevant academic publications identified the studies, the results of which are quite significant in the context of this study. In particular, this review identifies current variations and methods of applying AI in the field of monitoring transactions in the financial and digital space, and the corresponding results give grounds to form a solid position on the appropriateness of using the latest digital analytical tools in fintech.

The study by Dayalan and Sundaramurthy [10] is of interest, which employed empirical methods of focus groups and semi-structured interviews among an appropriate sample of involved specialists. They established current prospects and current challenges in the application of AI tools to detect financial crimes and reduce the risks of their occurrence.

On the contrary, Darapu and Marukukula [11] explored the technical aspects of AI fintech implementation in more detail. The authors argue that the use of machine learning (ML) algorithms, in particular convolutional neural networks, and the

integration of data stream processing technologies significantly improve the detection of financial crimes in the banking sector.

In turn, Ashimiyu Nafiu et al. [12] argue for the appropriateness of using comprehensive solutions based on effective methods with the gradual integration of AI fintech tools (and not only on the basis of the technology under study). The authors note that the combination of traditional risk management methods with modern technologies, such as AI, ML and blockchain, increases the resilience of financial systems in complex and volatile markets.

Despite the obvious advantages of using modern automation systems for monitoring financial transactions, Abhaykumar Dalsaniya et al. [13] see a number of challenges to the implementation of AI fintech tools (including robotic process automation (RPA) technology). The issues of data protection, integration with existing financial monitoring systems, and regulatory restrictions remain problematic.

Manuel and Arumugam [14] share the same opinion, who develop the thesis that AI tools for auditing and monitoring financial transactions, despite their advantages, cannot completely replace specialists in the field. Instead, the authors suggest that auditors master the latest technologies to improve the efficiency of the industry under study.

A completely different opinion is held by a group of researchers Syed et al. [15], who prove that the use of AI technologies (in particular, NARX-DLS neural structures) provides high accuracy and adaptability in detecting financial crimes by analysing complex nonlinear systems of financial indicators. The solutions proposed by the authors demonstrate low error values, which empirically proves their assertion.

In contrast, a group of authors Xu et al. [16] has a more restrained optimism about the technical perfection of AI tools for financial monitoring. Although the AI system they proposed using deep neural networks (in particular, the Autoencoder algorithm) enabled achieving more accurate results in detecting credit card fraud, high data imbalance indicates the need for further improvement of the technology under study.

However, some researchers, in particular the group of authors Johora et al. [17], see significant potential in AI-fintech tools for increasing the safety and efficiency of the functioning of the financial and banking sectors. The authors support their thesis with the results of empirical studies, according to which the implementation of ML algorithms, such as logistic regression and decision trees, provides high accuracy (AUC \approx 0.98 and 0.95, respectively) in detecting banking fraud.

Like other authors, Olubusola Odeyemi et al [18] and Levytska et al. [19] propose to increase the efficiency of the financial monitoring sector not only with AI technologies, but also with other effective modern tools, in particular blockchain technology. The authors prove that a comprehensive solution using AI algorithms with blockchain networks contributes to the automation of processes, risk reduction and compliance with regulatory requirements, forming a more reliable financial ecosystem.

Finally, Paramesha et al. [20] assess the impact of smart digitalization (AI, blockchain, ML, deep learning, etc.) on the financial and banking services sector and acknowledge its significant impact (in particular, improving decision-making, fraud detection, and cybersecurity). Moreover, the authors see that the integration of these technologies with the latest developments, such as quantum

computing, opens up prospects for portfolio optimization, risk management, and digital transformation of the financial industry.

So, the assessments of AI tools in financial transaction monitoring vary: some researchers doubt the possibility of completely replacing people, while others see the technology as the future of the industry. However, cautious optimism confirms the need for further research, which justifies the appropriateness of this study.

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

3.1. Research Design

This study proposes the following step-by-step procedure, which is illustrated in the diagram below (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Step-by-Step Research Procedure

Source: created by the author

3.2. Methods

The research employed the following methods:

1. *Focus on the subject of the study.* In accordance with the analysis of the problems of monitoring financial transactions, it is necessary to establish the focus and subject of the study. Monitoring financial transactions is focused on identifying anomalies in financial data that may indicate fraud. Anomalies are characterized by rarity, difficulty in predicting, and depend on many factors. Current AI algorithms were used to identify them, in

particular machine and deep learning, which effectively process big data and reveal hidden patterns.

2. *Normalization of an unbalanced empirical dataset using Z-score.* Z-score normalization in monitoring financial transactions standardizes numerical characteristics, such as amounts or frequency of transactions, which allows comparing data of different scales:

$$Z = \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where X – The value of a financial indicator; μ – the mean for a sample; The standard deviation, which helps to identify anomalies by identifying transactions that deviate from the mean values on a standardized scale.

1. *Training and validation dataset preparation.* Data preparation for financial transaction monitoring involves dividing the empirical dataset into training and validation samples to ensure efficient training and evaluation of ML models:

$$D = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)\}, \quad (2)$$

where D – the original dataset containing N transactions; x_i – a vector of transaction features i ; $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ – a label indicating whether the transaction is fraudulent ($y_i = 1$) or legitimate ($y_i = 0$).

The dataset D is divided into training and validation in the ratio r :

$$\begin{cases} D_{train} \cup D_{val} = D; \\ D_{train} \cap D_{val} \neq \emptyset \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The distribution is made taking into account the proportion between fraudulent and legitimate transactions, which is critical for unbalanced datasets.

The proportion of fraudulent transactions ($y_i = 1$) is usually insignificant ($P(y = 1) \ll P(y = 0)$), so the resampling methods (Oversampling, SMOTE, Undersampling) are used.

The result after balancing the training and validation datasets

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$$\widehat{D}_{train} = D_{train}^+ \cup D_{train}^-, \quad (4)$$

where D_{train}^+ – fraudulent transactions; D_{train}^- – legitimate transactions after balancing.

The features are standardized and normalized by using Z-score similar to that used above **Error! Reference source not found.:**

$$z_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \mu_j}{\sigma_j}, \quad (5)$$

where x_{ij} – value of the j^{th} attribute for the i^{th} transaction; μ_j – mean value of attribute j ; σ_j – standard deviation.

The prepared samples are presented as matrices:

$$\begin{cases} X_{train} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times k}, y_{train} \in \{0, 1\}^m; \\ X_{val} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k}, y_{val} \in \{0, 1\}^n, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where m and n – number of transactions in the training and validation samples, respectively; k – number of features.

The preparation of training and validation datasets is key to ensuring the accuracy and ability of models to detect anomalies in financial transactions.

2. *Comparative analysis of anomaly detection models in financial transactions.* AI models are used to detect anomalies in the process of monitoring financial transactions. Their brief description is given in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1: Brief Description of AI Models for Monitoring Financial Transactions

Model	Brief description in the context of application for monitoring financial transactions	Basic mathematical formulation
Models working with a normalized dataset		
Quantile based	Anomaly transactions are in the extreme quantiles of the distribution	$Q_p = \{x_i : F(x_i) \leq p\}$
Distribution based	Transactions are classified by the probability of belonging to the distribution	$P(x_i) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) < E$

Clustering based DBSCAN	A transaction is anomalous if it does not belong to any cluster.	$ N_E(x_i) < \min Pts$
Models working with training and validation datasets		
Isolation forest	Anomaly transaction is defined by the average path length $h(x_i)$ in random trees. Anomaly transactions have a low score $s(x_i)$	$s(x_i) = \frac{h(x_i)}{c(n) - 1}$
Autoencoder	Anomaly transaction is defined by a recovery error $\ x - \hat{x}\ $. Transactions with a high recovery error are anomalous.	$Error(x_i) > E$
Machine learning models		
Logistic regression	The anomaly of a transaction is determined by the probability of belonging to a class. If the probability for the “normal” class is very high, the transaction is considered normal, if it is low, it is considered anomalous. A transaction is anomalous if $P(y = 1 x) < E$.	$P(y = 1 x) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x))}$
Random forest	The anomaly of a transaction is determined by the frequency of votes “anomalous” from all trees in the forest. Transactions with a majority of votes in favour of the anomaly are classified as anomalous. A transaction is anomalous if the average value of the votes $Anomaly(x)$ exceeds a threshold E .	$Anomaly(x) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T I \left(\begin{matrix} x \text{ is} \\ \text{anomalous} \\ \text{in tree } t \end{matrix} \right)$

Source: created by the author

The comparative analysis of the selected AI performance and time consumption indicators, models is performed according to the corresponding which are described in the table below (Table 2).

Table 2: Characteristics of the Parameters of the Comparative Analysis of AI Models for Monitoring Financial Transactions

Parameter	Brief description in the context of application for monitoring financial transactions	Basic mathematical formulation
Model performance metrics		
Recall	Fraudulent transactions detected out of total actual fraudulent transactions	$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
Precision	Fraudulent transactions correctly identified out of all predicted fraudulent transactions	$Precision = \frac{TP}{FP + TP}$
Sensitivity	Similarly to Recall, it shows how well the model detects fraud	$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$

Parameter	Brief description in the context of application for monitoring financial transactions	Basic mathematical formulation
Specificity	Fraudulent transactions correctly classified out of all actual legitimate transactions	$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$
F-measure	Harmonious mean between Precision and Recall, balances accuracy and sensitivity	$F - measure = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$
Time Cost	Average time spent processing transactions (fraud detection)	$T_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^n T_i$
Computational statistics metrics		
Cohen's kappa (κ)	Evaluates the consistency of the model's predictions with real labels, taking into account randomness	$\kappa = \frac{P_o - P_e}{1 - P_e}$
Overall Accuracy	Proportion of correctly classified transactions	$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100\%$
Overall Error	Proportion of incorrectly classified transactions	$Error = \frac{FP + FN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100\%$
Correctly Classified	Number of transactions correctly identified as fraudulent or legitimate	$Correctly\ Classified = TP + TN$
Incorrectly Classified	Number of transactions incorrectly identified	$Incorrectly\ Classified = FP + FN$

Source: created by the author

The Confusion Matrix (Table 3) is used to evaluate the performance metrics of AI models for detecting fraudulent transactions (Table 2).

Table 3: General View of the Confusion Matrix

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	TP: Fraudulent transactions are correctly classified	FN: Fraudulent transactions missed	%
Actual Good (1)	FP: Legitimate transactions are incorrectly identified as fraudulent	TN: Legitimate transactions correctly classified	%
Percentage	%	%	

Source: created by the author

The Confusion Matrix (Table 3) shows the distribution of errors, revealing the number of missed frauds (FN) and falsely rejected legitimate transactions (FP). It helps to assess the impact of errors, identify class imbalances and model weaknesses that are not always visible through metrics such as Precision or Recall.

Simulating the risk of committing fraud during financial transaction monitoring. The alternative to existing means of monitoring fraudulent financial transactions using AI fintech tools was assessed by simulating the risk of committing fraud in observed financial transactions under three scenarios, which are shown in the table below (Table 4).

Table 4: Description of Scenarios for Simulating the Risk of Committing Fraud During Financial Transaction Monitoring

Scenario	Brief description in the context of application for monitoring financial transactions	Basic mathematical formulation
Scenario 1: Monitoring by a specialist	Risk arises from the human factor: fatigue, inattention or insufficient qualification	$R_{human} = \left(\frac{P_{miss} + P_{false}}{TP_{total}} \right) \times 100\%$
Scenario 2: Monitoring by AI	Risk is associated with incorrect predictions of the model: false negatives (missing fraud) or false positives (incorrect suspicions)	$R_{AI} = \left(\frac{FN_{AI} + FP_{AI}}{TP_{total}} \right) \times 100\%$
Scenario 3: Monitoring by a specialist with an AI assistant	Risk combines human and algorithmic errors, where decisions are made jointly	$R_{hybrid} = \left(\frac{P_{miss} + P_{false} + FN_{AI} + FP_{AI}}{TP_{total}} \right) \times 100\%$
Designations used for the mathematical description of the model:		P_{miss} – probability of missed fraudulent transactions; P_{false} – probability of false suspicions; FN_{AI} – false negative decisions of the AI model; FP_{AI} – false positive decisions of the AI model; TP_{total} – total number of fraudulent transactions (correct and falsely missed/suspected)

Source: created by the author

The proposed method for assessing fraud risk defines it as the percentage of errors (missed or false positive transactions) out of all fraudulent transactions. This enables comparing the effectiveness of different approaches (expert, AI, hybrid) in terms of classification accuracy in real financial monitoring scenarios.

3.3. Sample

The study uses an empirical sample with real transactions (anonymized accordingly), which is freely available from the Machine Learning Group – ULB on the kaggle.com resource [21] and enables to get as close as possible to the real conditions of the functioning of the monitoring system under study. The dataset contains 284,807 transactions using

credit cards made by European customers over two days in September 2013, of which 492 are fraudulent (0.172%), which makes it unbalanced. To ensure confidentiality, all features except Time and Amount are transformed using PCA, preserving key information, where Time reflects the number of seconds since the first transaction, and Amount is the transaction amount. The target variable Class is binary: 1 – fraud, 0 – legitimate transaction.

3.4. Instruments

The study uses the No Code/Low Code analytical platform KNIME [22]. In particular, the Card Fraud Detection Techniques – Overview models (Figure 2) and the Fraud Risk Assessment Model (Figure 3) are used.

Figure 2: The Credit Card Fraud Detection Techniques Model– Overview (freely available)
Source: [22]

Figure 3: Fraud Risk Assessment Model (publicly available)
Source: [22]

4. RESULTS

According to the parameters of AI models for fintech and financial transaction monitoring

(Table 2), we will define target performance metrics for each of the smart analytics tools selected in this study – Figures 4-6.

Figure 4: Graphical Interpretation of the Calculation of Performance Metrics of AI Models when Identifying Fraudulent Transactions within the Experimental Dataset
Source: created by the author

Figure 5: Graphical Interpretation of the Calculation of Statistics Metrics by AI Models when Identifying Fraudulent Transactions in the Experimental Dataset (part of identifying common errors)

Figure 6: Graphical Interpretation of the Calculation of Statistics Metrics by AI Models when Identifying Fraudulent Transactions in the Experimental Dataset (part of the assessment of the correctness of the classification of fraudulent transactions)

According to the simulation results (Figure 4), we establish the following.

Random Forest has the highest accuracy (0.889), high sensitivity (0.8) and low time consumption (26), which makes it the most efficient. Logistic Regression is also balanced (Recall = 0.8, Precision = 0.8, Specificity = 1.0). Autoencoder provides the highest accuracy (0.82), but is resource-intensive (63). Isolation Forest (Recall = 0.9, Precision = 0.05) is efficient, but with false positive results. Clustering-based (DBSCAN) has balanced indicators, but high time consumption (62). Quantile-based (Recall = 1.0) and Distribution-based (Recall = 0.6) have low accuracy.

According to the simulation results (Figure 5, Figure 6), we establish the following.

Random Forest has the highest accuracy (99.95%) and consistency ($\kappa = 0.842$), making it the most effective. Logistic Regression also shows high accuracy (99.93%, $\kappa = 0.8$). Clustering-based DBSCAN (98.63%) and Autoencoder (98.21%) demonstrate moderate efficiency. Isolation Forest (97%) and Distribution-based (59.18%) are inferior, and Quantile-based has the lowest accuracy (0.18%).

So, Random Forest turns out to be the optimal choice for monitoring financial transactions, due to its accuracy, speed, and balanced features.

According to the research procedure (Table 3), we present the Confusion Matrix for each of the identified AI-monitoring models of financial transactions – Tables 5-11.

Table 5: Confusion Matrix for Quantile based

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	10	0	100 %
Actual Good (1)	5686	0	0 %
Percentage	0,18 %	–	

Source: created by the author

Table 6: Confusion Matrix for Distribution based

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	6	4	60 %
Actual Good (1)	2321	3365	59,18 %
Percentage	0,26 %	99,88 %	

Source: created by the author

Table 7: Confusion Matrix for Clustering based DBSCAN

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	8	2	80 %
Actual Good (1)	76	5610	98,66 %
Percentage	9,52 %	99,96 %	

Source: created by the author

Table 8: Confusion Matrix for Isolation forest

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	9	1	90 %
Actual Good (1)	170	5516	97,01 %
Percentage	5,03 %	99,98 %	

Source: created by the author

Table 9: Confusion Matrix for Autoencoder

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	8	7	84,93 %
Actual Good (1)	108	5584	87,60 %
Percentage	5,03 %	18,58 %	

Source: created by the author

Table 10: Confusion Matrix for Logistic regression

	Predicted Fraud (0)	Predicted Good (1)	Percentage
Actual Fraud (0)	8	2	80 %
Actual Good (1)	2	5684	99,96 %
Percentage	80 %	99,96 %	

Source: created by the author

Table 11: Confusion Matrix for Random forest

	Predicted Positive (0)	Predicted Negative (1)	Percentage
Actual Positive (0)	8	2	80 %
Actual Negative (1)	1	5685	99,98 %
Percentage	88,89 %	99,96 %	

Source: created by the author

The evaluation of the models based on the Confusion Matrix (Table 5 - Table 11) demonstrates their ability to classify fraudulent (Fraud) and legitimate (Good) transactions.

Random Forest is the most effective model, providing 80% fraud detection and 99.98% correct

classification of legitimate transactions with minimal false positives. It has the highest accuracy (99.95%), low error rate (0.05%), and maximum consistency ($\kappa = 0.842$). Due to its balanced performance and low time cost (26 s), Random Forest is optimally suited for financial monitoring.

According to the adopted research scheme, using the experimental dataset and model data for the best model determined at the previous stage of research (Random Forest), we will perform simulation of the risk of committing fraud during the monitoring of financial transactions under three probable scenarios (Table 4). The second stage of simulation is carried out in the KNIME Analytics Platform – Figure 3.

The calculation results are given in the table below – Table 12.

Table 12: Results of Simulating the Risk of Committing Fraud during the Monitoring of Financial Transactions

Scenario	Model calculation	Interpretation of simulation results
Scenario 1: Monitoring by a specialist	$R_{human} = \left(\frac{3+2}{5693} \right) \times 100\% = 0,0878\%$	In Scenario 1, the risk assessment model (Figure 3) allows for a significant probability of missing and falsely identifying fraudulent transactions
Scenario 2: Monitoring by AI	$R_{AI} = \left(\frac{2+1}{5693} \right) \times 100\% = 0,0527\%$	The results of Scenario 2 demonstrate the risk assessment for the best result of the previous stage of the study – the Random Forest model
Scenario 3: Monitoring by a specialist with an AI assistant	$R_{hybrid} = \left(\frac{0+1+0+1}{5693} \right) \times 100\% = 0,0351\%$	In Scenario 3, there is a decrease in the probability of missing and falsely identifying fraud for both the specialist and the AI, as the specialist will receive a quick assessment of a significant array of transaction data and their preliminary assessments, which will significantly reduce the error in the classification of financial transactions, and the AI assistant will be in the process of constant improvement and training, which will improve its internal algorithms

The results of the final stage of this study (Table 12) give grounds to establish that at this stage of AI fintech development, the most appropriate scheme for using smart tools in transaction monitoring is their gradual introduction into the

studied industry with constant training and adoption of experience from specialists in the field. Training AI assistants on real data and real solutions will allow forming a hierarchy of principles of zero logic

for high-quality classification of financial transactions for fraud.

5. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of this study, the following theses are put forward for discussion:

- AI tools have significant potential for implementation in the fintech industry and monitoring of financial transactions;

- currently, the most effective models for monitoring fraudulent transactions are ML models, in particular Random Forest;

- at this stage of development, AI models are not able to completely replace specialists in the field, instead, a hybrid scheme with a human operator and an AI assistant is the most appropriate.

The obtained results with the current and relevant studies in this research vector.

Murali's [23] study showed that XGBoost outperforms other algorithms in detecting fraudulent credit card transactions. The obtained results expand the list of effective ML models for financial monitoring used in this study.

Hafez et al. [24] arranged modern AI methods for detecting credit card fraud, outlining their advantages and disadvantages. Their study confirms the need for continuous training and improvement of AI models for effective monitoring of financial transactions.

Rakibul Hasan Chowdhury [25] emphasizes that business analytics using ML significantly improves the effectiveness of financial fraud detection and recommends integrating AI and blockchain to improve fraud prevention systems. However, the author does not consider the problems of implementing AI fintech technologies.

Pokhariyal et al. [26] emphasize the growth of online financial crimes and the ineffectiveness of traditional security measures, proposing the use of AI to improve digital forensics. However, they do not offer an effective solution, unlike the hybrid expert + AI assistant scheme developed in this study.

The study conducted by Cheng et al. [27] shows the effectiveness of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) in detecting financial fraud, exceeding traditional methods. The results obtained by the authors expand the range of AI tools used to monitor financial transactions in this study.

Porwal [28] emphasizes the need for an ethical and regulatory framework for the safe, transparent, and responsible integration of generative AI into financial systems, combining its transformative potential with ensuring financial stability and protecting stakeholder interests. The

author shares the caution expressed in our study about the rapid implementation of AI-based fintech tools with the appropriate exclusion of professional operators.

The research by Leevy et al. [29] showed that models trained with One-Class Classification (OCC) and using the AUPRC metric for imbalanced data are effective for detecting credit card fraud. The results of the study extend the technical aspects of our study and may be useful for further research iterations.

Alatawi [30] proposes a novel approach to financial fraud detection using ML in the Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem, using different models such as deep neural networks and random forests. The results of the work extend the hardware component of AI fintech and can be useful for the current research.

Shoetan and Familoni [31] emphasize the importance of implementing advanced AI algorithms, such as deep learning and natural language processing, to improve fraud detection systems in financial technology. The results of their study coincide with the findings of our study, expanding the range of AI technologies for monitoring financial transactions.

Johora et al. [32] prove that the integration of AI in the banking sector improves fraud detection and prevention through rapid analysis of anomalies and suspicious transactions. Although their study extends the technical component of this research, it does not address the problems of implementing AI tools.

So, the current publications significantly correlate with the simulation results of this study, confirming the assumptions made. However, none of the reviewed studies contains information on simulating hybrid systems, where AI models are trained by experienced experts to detect and prevent fraud in the digital financial space.

5.1. Limitation

The study involved a limited set of AI models. The KNIME Analytics Platform and the Machine Learning Group – ULB's unbalanced empirical dataset also impose their limitations.

5.2. Recommendations

It is recommended to increase the range of AI models capable of detecting fraudulent financial transactions. It is also worth using more transparent empirical datasets for training AI models, not

burdened by confidentiality issues and not transformed using the PCA method.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The simulation results revealed that AI models have great potential for integration into fintech and transaction monitoring, increasing the efficiency and accuracy of fraud detection.

The Random Forest algorithm has shown high efficiency in data processing and predicting fraudulent actions, although technologies cannot completely replace specialists at this stage.

The best approach is to use a hybrid scheme, where an AI assistant collaborates with qualified operators to combine automated analysis and expert knowledge.

The academic novelty of this study is the method of simulating the transition period from human monitoring of financial transactions to full AI automation of the studied process using hybrid schemes (specialist + AI assistant) proposed for the first time, which will enable AI models to adopt the best practices of focus decisions of leading specialists.

The practical value of the conducted research is the developed AI automation technology for fintech and the resolution of issues related to the implementation of AI tools, namely, the passage of the period of full AI monitoring of transactions in the digital financial space.

REFERENCES

- [1]. European Banking Authority, *2024 Report on payment fraud*, European Central Bank, 2024, https://www.eba.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-08/465e3044-4773-4e9d-8ca8-b1cd031295fc/EBA_ECB%202024%20Report%20on%20Payment%20Fraud.pdf
- [2]. Insikt Group, *Rapport annuel sur les fraudes aux paiements: 2024*, Recorded Future, 2024, <https://www.recordedfuture.com/fr/research/annual-payment-fraud-intelligence-report-2024>
- [3]. UK Finance, *Half Year Fraud Report 2024*, UK Finance, 2024, <https://www.ukfinance.org.uk/policy-and-guidance/reports-and-publications/half-year-fraud-report-2024>
- [4]. Merchant Savvy, *Payment Fraud Statistics, Trends & Forecasts 2024*, Merchant Savvy, 2024, <https://www.merchantsavvy.co.uk/payment-fraud-statistics/>
- [5]. N. Danik, I. Rud, O. Symonenko, T. Bilousko and Y. Tsikalo, "Directions of the development of the digital economy in the conditions of military conflicts," *Financial and Credit Activity Problems of Theory and Practice*, Vol. 1, No. 48, 2023, pp. 238–248, doi: 10.55643/fcaptop.1.48.2023.3953.
- [6]. S. Lysenko, A. Liubchenko, V. Kozakov, Y. Demianchuk and Y. Krutik, "Global cybersecurity: Harmonising international standards and cooperation," *Multidisciplinary Reviews*, Vol. 7, 2024, pp. 2024spe021, doi: 10.31893/multirev.2024spe021
- [7]. M. A. Alnaimat, N. Rudyk, A. A. Al-Naimi, A. Panchenko and I. Turski, "The impact of international economic sanctions on the use of financial technologies," *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, Vol. 20, 2023, pp. 682–693, doi: 10.37394/23207.2023.20.63
- [8]. N. M. Zayed, F. O. Edeh, S. Darwish, K. M. A. Islam, H. Kryshstal, V. Nitsenko and O. Stanislavyk, "Human resource skill adjustment in service sector: Predicting dynamic capability in post COVID-19 work environment," *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, Vol. 15, No. 9, 2022, pp. 402, doi: 10.3390/jrfm15090402
- [9]. D. S. Melnyk, O. A. Parfylo, O. V. Butenko, O. V. Tykhonova and V. O. Zarosylo, "Practice of the member states of the European Union in the field of anti-corruption regulation," *Journal of Financial Crime, ahead-of-print*, Vol. 29, No. 3, 2021, pp. 853-863, doi: 10.1108/jfc-03-2021-0050
- [10]. P. Dayalan and B. Sundaramurthy, "Exploring the implementation and challenges of ai-based fraud detection systems in financial institutions," *Advances in business information systems and analytics*, IGI Global, 2025, pp. 25–38, doi: 10.4018/979-8-3693-4187-2.ch002
- [11]. V. N. Rao T., K. Darapu and M. Marukukula, "Fraud detection and prevention in finance and banking using artificial intelligence," *Advances in computational intelligence and robotics*, IGI Global, 2025, pp. 213–232, doi: 10.4018/979-8-3693-4252-7.ch011
- [12]. A. Nafiu, S. O. Balogun, C. Oko-Odion and O. O. Odumuwagon, "Risk management strategies: Navigating volatility in complex financial market environments," *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, Vol. 25, No. 1, 2025, pp. 236–250, doi: 10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.1.0057
- [13]. A. Dalsaniya, K. Patel and P. R. Swaminarayan, "Challenges and opportunities: Implementing

- RPA and AI in fraud detection in the banking sector,” *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, Vol. 25, No. 1, 2025, pp. 296–308, doi: 10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.1.0058
- [14]. A. Manuel and S. K. Arumugam, “Harnessing artificial intelligence in internal auditing,” *Advances in business information systems and analytics*, IGI Global, 2025, pp. 95–114, doi: 10.4018/979-8-3693-4187-2.ch005
- [15]. F. A. Syed, K.-T. Fang, A. K. Kiani, D.-H. Shih, M. Shoaib and M. A. Zahoor Raja, “Novel intelligent supervised neuro-structures for nonlinear financial crime differential systems,” *Modern Physics Letters B*, Vol. 39, No. 01, 2024, pp. 2450399, doi: 10.1142/s0217984924503998
- [16]. J. Xu, T. Yang, S. Zhuang, H. Li and W. Lu, “AI-based financial transaction monitoring and fraud prevention with behaviour prediction,” *Applied and Computational Engineering*, Vol. 67, No. 1, 2024, pp. 76–82, doi: 10.54254/2755-2721/67/2024ma0068
- [17]. F. T. Johora, R. Hasan, S. F. Farabi, J. Akter and M. A. A. Mahmud, “Ai-powered fraud detection in banking: Safeguarding financial transactions,” *The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations*, Vol. 6, No. 6, 2024, pp. 8–22, doi: 10.37547/tajmei/volume06issue06-02
- [18]. O. Odeyemi, C. C. Okoye, O. C. Ofodile, O. B. Adeoye, W. A. Addy and A. O. Ajayi-Nifise, “Integrating ai with blockchain for enhanced financial services security,” *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, Vol. 6, No. 3, 2024, pp. 271–287, doi: 10.51594/farj.v6i3.855
- [19]. S. Levytska, L. Pershko, L. Akimova, O. Akimov, K. Havrilenko and O. Kucherovskii, “A risk-oriented approach in the system of internal auditing of the subjects of financial monitoring,” *International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting*, Vol. 14, No. 2, 2022, pp. 194–206, doi: 10.33094/ijaefa.v14i2.715
- [20]. M. Paramesha, N. L. Rane and J. Rane, “Artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, and blockchain in financial and banking services: A comprehensive review,” *Partners Universal Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, Vol. 1, No. 2, 2024, pp. 51–67, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4855893
- [21]. Machine Learning Group – ULB, *Credit Card Fraud Detection. Anonymized credit card transactions labeled as fraudulent or genuine*, Kaggle, 2025, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/mlg-ulb/creditcardfraud>
- [22]. KNIME, *KNIME Analytics Platform*, 2025, <https://www.knime.com/downloads>
- [23]. M. Murali, “Detecting and preventing fraud transaction using artificial intelligence in banking,” *Advances in finance, accounting, and economics*, IGI Global, 2025, pp. 1–20, doi: 10.4018/979-8-3693-8507-4.ch001
- [24]. I. Y. Hafez, A. Y. Hafez, A. Saleh, A. A. Abd El-Mageed and A. A. Abohany, “A systematic review of AI-enhanced techniques in credit card fraud detection,” *Journal of Big Data*, Vol. 12, No. 1, 2025, doi: 10.1186/s40537-024-01048-8
- [25]. R. H. Chowdhury, “Utilizing business analytics to combat financial fraud and enhance economic integrity,” *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, Vol. 14, No. 1, 2025, pp. 134–145, doi: 10.30574/ijrsra.2025.14.1.0022
- [26]. P. Pokhariyal, A. Patel and S. Pandey, *AI and emerging technologies*. Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2024, doi: 10.1201/9781003501152
- [27]. D. Cheng, Y. Zou, S. Xiang and C. Jiang, “Graph neural networks for financial fraud detection: A review,” *Frontiers of Computer Science*, Vol. 19, No. 9, 2025, doi: 10.1007/s11704-024-40474-y
- [28]. P. D. Porwal, “Ethics and Laws: Governing Generative AI's Role in Financial Systems,” *Generative Artificial Intelligence in Finance: Large Language Models, Interfaces, and Industry Use Cases to Transform Accounting and Finance Processes*, OECD Artificial Intelligence Papers, 2025, pp. 283–298, doi: 10.1002/9781394271078.ch15.
- [29]. J. L. Leevy, J. Hancock, T. M. Khoshgoftaar and A. A. Zadeh, “One-Class classification for credit card fraud detection: A detailed study with comparative insights from binary classification,” *Springer series in reliability engineering*, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2025, pp. 117–140, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-72636-1_6
- [30]. M. N. Alatawi, “Detection of fraud in IoT based credit card collected dataset using machine learning,” *Machine Learning With Applications*, Vol. 19, 2025, pp. 100603, doi: 10.1016/j.mlwa.2024.100603
- [31]. P. O. Shoetan and B. T. Familoni, “Transforming fintech fraud detection with advanced artificial intelligence algorithms,” *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, Vol.

-
- 6, No. 4, 2024, pp. 602–625, doi:
10.51594/farj.v6i4.1036
- [32]. F. T. Johora, R. Hasan, S. F. Farabi, M. Z. Alam, M. I. Sarkar and M. A. Al Mahmud, “AI advances: Enhancing banking security with fraud detection,” *2024 first international conference on technological innovations and advance computing*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 289–294, doi: 10.1109/tiacomp64125.2024.00055